

MANAGING INNOVATION ACTIVITY OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED BUSINESSES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE ECONOMY**Akimov Damir Slyambekovich,***doctoral degree in DBA**Almaty Management University AlmaU***Konyrbekov Medet,***PhD, Associate Professor, Institute of Economics, Committee of Science of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan***Makhabbat Zhamkeyeva***PhD, JSC "Kazakhstan Industry and Export Center QazIndustry",
Astana, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

The article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of managing the innovation activity of small and medium-sized businesses in the context of the digital transformation of the economy. The relevance of the research is due to the increasing role of small and medium-sized enterprises in providing employment, diversifying the economy, developing the domestic market and creating an innovative environment. The materials of the Republic of Kazakhstan show that the SME sector is a significant element of the national economy: as of January 1, 2025, 2,262.4 thousand were registered in the country. There were 2,071.7 thousand SMEs, of which 2,071.7 thousand were active; the number of people employed in the sector reached 4,422.1 thousand people, and output in 2024 amounted to 81,920.0 billion tenge [1]. At the same time, the level of innovative activity of enterprises remains insufficiently high and, according to official statistics, amounted to about 11.9% in 2024 [3]. This indicates that there is a gap between the scale of the business sector and its ability to systematically implement technological, organizational and marketing innovations. The article substantiates the need to move from fragmented implementation of digital solutions to a comprehensive innovation management model that includes digital infrastructure, access to finance, competence development, platform integration and institutional support.

Keywords: small and medium-sized businesses, innovation activity, digital transformation, entrepreneurship, digital platforms, Kazakhstan, innovation management.

Introduction. In modern conditions, digital transformation is becoming one of the key factors in increasing the competitiveness of the national economy. The development of digital technologies, electronic commerce, artificial intelligence, big data, cloud services, and platform-based business models is changing traditional approaches to organizing entrepreneurial activity. This process is especially important for small and medium-sized businesses, as SMEs have high flexibility, the ability to quickly adapt to changes in demand, and the potential to introduce new products, services, and business processes.

For Kazakhstan, the problem of managing the innovation activity of SMEs is of particular relevance. On the one hand, small and medium-sized businesses demonstrate steady quantitative growth. According to the Bureau of National Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as of January 1, 2025, the number of registered SMEs amounted to 2,262.4 thousand units, which is 3.8% more than on the same date in 2024. The number of operating SMEs reached 2,071,700 units, an increase of 3.5% [1]. On the other hand, the innovative activity of enterprises remains limited, which hinders the transition of SMEs from extensive growth to high-quality development.

The digital transformation of the economy creates new opportunities for small and medium-sized businesses: expanding sales markets through e-commerce, reducing transaction costs, automating management processes, using digital marketing, implementing CRM and ERP systems, developing fintech tools and platform interaction with consumers. In 2025, the volume

of retail electronic commerce in Kazakhstan, including marketplaces, amounted to 3,768.8 billion tenge, and its share in the total retail trade reached 14.3% [2]. This shows that digital channels are becoming not an auxiliary, but an independent direction for the development of entrepreneurial activity.

The purpose of the article is to study the features of managing the innovative activity of small and medium-sized businesses in the context of the digital transformation of the economy and to develop ways to increase the effectiveness of innovative development of SMEs.

Literature review. In the scientific literature, the innovative activity of business entities is considered as the ability of enterprises to create, adapt and implement new products, technologies, organizational solutions and methods of promotion. According to the classical approach of J. Schumpeter, innovations are the basis of entrepreneurial development and act as a source of economic dynamics [8]. In modern conditions, this idea takes on new content, as innovations are increasingly associated not only with industrial technologies, but also with digital platforms, data, algorithms, service models and network effects.

International studies show that the digital transformation of SMEs depends not only on the availability of technology, but also on managerial competencies, organizational culture, access to finance, and the ability of enterprises to use data for decision-making [9]. Small and medium-sized businesses are characterized by limited financial and human resources, so innovation often takes place not through large research units,

but through the gradual adaptation of ready-made digital solutions: online sales, mobile payments, cloud services, CRM systems, digital analytics and automated accounting.

In Kazakhstan, the issues of digitalization of entrepreneurship are considered in the context of the state policy on the development of the digital economy. International ratings show a certain progress of the country in the field of digital governance. In particular, Kazakhstan ranked 24th among 193 countries in the UN e-Government Development Index in 2024 [5]. This creates favorable institutional conditions for the development of digital services, however, a high level of digitalization of public services does not always automatically translate into high innovation activity of the private sector.

According to WIPO, Kazakhstan ranked 81st in the Global Innovation Index among 139 economies in 2025 [6]. This indicator indicates the need to strengthen the national innovation system, especially in terms of technology commercialization, research and development, increasing the digital maturity of enterprises and stimulating innovation in the SME sector.

Materials and methods of research. The methodological basis of the article consists of systematic, comparative, statistical and analytical approaches. Data from the Bureau of National Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the World Bank, the United Nations, WIPO, Network Readiness Index, as well as scientific publications on innovation management and digital transformation of small and medium-sized businesses were used as an information base.

The study was conducted in several stages.

At the first stage, the role of SMEs in the Kazakh economy was analyzed based on indicators of the number of registered and operating entities, the number of employees, output and contribution to GDP.

At the second stage, the indicators of digital transformation were considered, including the development of e-commerce, the use of marketplaces, the expansion of digital infrastructure and Kazakhstan's position in international digital ratings.

At the third stage, an assessment of the problems of managing the innovation activity of SMEs was given and directions for its improvement were proposed.

The following indicators were used for the analysis:

1. the number of registered and active SMEs;
2. the number of people employed in the SME sector;
3. Production by SMEs;
4. the share of SMEs in GDP;
5. E-commerce volume;
6. the share of e-commerce in retail turnover;
7. the level of innovative activity of enterprises;
8. Kazakhstan's position in the international indices of digital and innovative development.

The results of the study. The analysis shows that small and medium-sized businesses occupy a stable and growing place in the economic system of Kazakhstan, acting simultaneously as a source of employment, entrepreneurial initiative, product output and potential basis for innovative development. According to the Bureau of National Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as of January 1, 2025, 2,262,392 small and medium-sized businesses were registered in the country, while on the same date in 2024 their number was 2,178,951 units. Thus, during the period under review, the number of registered SMEs increased by 83,441 units, or 3.8% [1]. This dynamic indicates the continued positive entrepreneurial activity, despite structural constraints related to access to finance, the level of digital maturity, and the heterogeneity of the regional business environment.

Simultaneously with the growth of the total number of registered entities, there is an increase in the number of actually operating enterprises. As of January 1, 2025, the number of operating SMEs amounted to 2,071,657 units, which is 69,458 units, or 3.5% more than on January 1, 2024 [1]. The share of operating entities in the total number of registered SMEs has reached 91.6%, which suggests a fairly high degree of involvement of business structures in economic activity. At the same time, the quantitative expansion of the sector does not always mean qualitative growth, since innovation activity depends not only on the number of enterprises, but also on their ability to implement new technologies, management solutions, digital tools and modern business models.

Table 1

Key indicators of SME development in Kazakhstan

Indicator	2024 / as of 01.01.2024	2025 / as of 01.01.2025	Change
Registered SMEs, units	2 178 951	2 262 392	+3,8%
Operating entities of SMEs, units	2 002 199	2 071 657	+3,5%
Employed in SMEs, people	4 326 316	4 422 058	+2,2%
SME output, billion tenge	68 710,5	81 920,0	+11,5%
The share of SMEs in GDP, January–September 2024	-	39,3%	+2,8 п.п.
Note - compiled according to [1].			

The importance of small and medium-sized businesses is manifested not only in the quantitative growth of subjects, but also in its contribution to employment. The number of people employed in the SME sector as of January 1, 2025 amounted to 4,422.1 thousand people, which is 2.2% higher than in the previous year [1]. This confirms the socio-economic role of SMEs as one

of the key mechanisms for creating jobs and maintaining household incomes. At the same time, the growth of employment in the SME sector in the context of digital transformation acquires a new content: there is an increasing need not only for traditional labor resources, but also for specialists with digital competencies,

online sales tools, data analytics, automated accounting, digital marketing and customer service management.

The economic contribution of SMEs is also characterized by a positive dynamics. The output of small and medium-sized enterprises in January–December 2024 amounted to 81,920.0 billion tenge, an increase of 11.5% compared to the previous year [1]. This growth indicates the expansion of the manufacturing and service activity of the enterprise sector. At the same time, to ensure the long-term sustainability of the economy, it is important that an increase in output is accompanied not only by an increase in volumes, but also by technological upgrades, increased productivity, the introduction of digital solutions and the transition to more complex forms of value creation.

The digital transformation of the business environment is of particular importance in the context of innovation management. One of the most visible indicators of the digitalization of SMEs is the development of e-commerce. According to official statistics, the volume of retail e-commerce in Kazakhstan, including marketplaces, in 2025 amounted to 3,768.8 billion tenge, whereas in 2021 this figure was 482.0 billion tenge [2]. Consequently, in 2021-2025, the volume of retail e-commerce increased almost 7.8 times. This dynamic indicates an accelerated expansion of digital sales channels and the formation of new models of interaction between businesses and consumers.

Table 2

Dynamics of electronic commerce in Kazakhstan

Indicator	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
The volume of retail electronic commerce, billion tenge	482,0	1 963,5	2 439,8	3 156,4	3 768,8
The share of e-commerce in retail trade, %	3,6	12,5	12,7	14,1	14,3
Volume of e-commerce services, billion tenge	349,9	1 186,5	1 602,6	2 443,4	2 477,3
Note - compiled according to [2].					

The growth of e-commerce reflects not only a change in consumer behavior, but also a transformation in the management practices of SMEs. For small and medium-sized enterprises, digital sales channels are becoming a tool for expanding the market, reducing transaction costs, optimizing logistics, improving communication with customers and increasing the speed of order processing. If earlier the digitalization of entrepreneurship was often perceived as an auxiliary element of promotion, now it becomes part of the innovative strategy of the enterprise.

Marketplaces play a particularly significant role in the development of digital entrepreneurship. In 2025, marketplaces accounted for 86% of the retail e-commerce volume, while enterprises' own Internet resources accounted for 14% [2]. This shows that platform solutions have become the most accessible channel for small and medium-sized businesses to enter the digital market. Marketplaces provide entrepreneurs with access to a wide consumer audience, payment infrastructure, logistics services, and promotion tools. At the same time, high dependence on external platforms creates certain management risks associated with limited control over customer data, commission costs, dependence on platform rules and reduced independence in brand formation. In this regard, effective management of SME innovation activity should include not only the use of marketplaces, but also the development of its own digital channels, customer bases, loyalty systems and sales analytics.

The development of digital commerce and the platform economy requires an appropriate infrastructure base. For SMEs, access to high-quality Internet, digital payment systems, cloud services and logistics solutions is a prerequisite for the implementation of innovations. In this regard, it is important to expand the digital infrastructure in the regions, since it is precisely regional differences in access to technology that limit

the uniform development of innovative entrepreneurship. The financing of the Kazakhstan Digital Acceleration for an Inclusive Economy project, aimed at expanding broadband access in underserved regions of the country, indicates the recognition of digital infrastructure as one of the key conditions for economic integration and entrepreneurship development [4].

Despite the positive dynamics of digitalization, the level of innovative activity of enterprises in Kazakhstan remains insufficiently high. According to official statistics, in 2024, the innovative activity of enterprises was about 11.9% [3]. This means that only a limited number of enterprises systematically implement product, process, organizational or marketing innovations. Consequently, there is a significant gap between the scale of the SME sector and the level of its innovative involvement. This gap is explained by a number of factors, including limited access to financing for innovative projects, a lack of digital competencies, weak integration of science and business, low willingness of enterprises to manage data, and the fragmented nature of digital technology adoption.

In practice, many SMEs use digital tools primarily for individual operations, for example, to promote goods on social networks, accept online orders, or work through marketplaces. However, more complex elements of digital transformation, including CRM systems, ERP solutions, big data analytics, warehouse accounting automation, demand forecasting, and the use of artificial intelligence, remain less common. This indicates that the innovative activity of SMEs should be considered not only as a result of the introduction of individual technologies, but also as a controlled process of organizational development.

In this regard, the management of innovation activity of small and medium-sized businesses should be based on an integrated model combining strategic planning, digital technologies, financial instruments, human

capital development and institutional support. An enterprise's innovation strategy should include defining digitalization goals, evaluating resources, selecting priority technologies, calculating the expected effect, and

monitoring the results. Only with such a strategy can digital transformation move from the elemental implementation of individual solutions to the systematic management of innovative development.

Table 3

The SME Innovation Activity management model

The model element	Content	Expected effect
Innovative strategy	Goals, indicators, and an innovation plan	The transition from random digitalization to system management
Digital technologies	CRM, ERP, e-commerce, Big Data, AI, cloud services	Cost reduction, sales growth, improved quality of solutions
Financing	Grants, preferential loans, guarantees, digital vouchers	Increasing the availability of innovative projects
Competencies	Training of entrepreneurs and employees	The growth of digital maturity of SMEs
and the institutional environment	Technology parks, accelerators, infrastructure, IP protection	Formation of an innovation ecosystem
Note - compiled by the author.		

The presented model shows that the innovative activity of SMEs is formed under the influence of not one, but a combination of interrelated factors. Digital technologies create an instrumental basis for innovation, but their effectiveness depends on financial accessibility, staff qualifications, managerial readiness of the enterprise and the quality of the institutional environment. Therefore, measures to support SMEs should be aimed not only at subsidizing individual costs, but also at creating a sustainable innovation ecosystem.

An important area of increasing innovation activity is the development of digital maturity of enterprises. This requires the introduction of diagnostic tools that allow assessing the degree of digitalization of a business by such parameters as online sales, automated accounting, the use of CRM systems, digital marketing, data analytics, information security and integration with platforms. Such diagnostics will make it possible to identify the real needs of enterprises and form targeted support measures.

An equally important area is the expansion of SMEs' access to digital finance. The use of fintech tools, scoring models, digital applications, and alternative data can increase the availability of loans and grants for innovative projects. This is especially important for start-up entrepreneurs, companies from the regions and enterprises that do not have sufficient collateral. At the same time, financial support should be linked to specific results of digitalization: software implementation, automation of processes, entry into new markets, increased productivity and sales growth.

Thus, the results of the study confirm that digital transformation creates significant opportunities for increasing the innovative activity of small and medium-sized businesses. However, the realization of these opportunities requires a transition from the fragmented use of digital tools to the systematic management of innovative development. This is especially important for Kazakhstan, as the SME sector already has a significant economic scale, but its innovative potential is not yet fully exploited. Increasing the innovative activity of SMEs should become one of the key directions of state economic policy, regional development and entrepreneurial strategies in the digital economy.

Discussion. The results of the study show that Kazakhstan has significant entrepreneurial potential, but the innovation activity of SMEs does not yet correspond to the scale of the sector. On the one hand, there is an increase in the number of operating SME entities in the country, an increase in employment and an expansion in output. On the other hand, the innovation activity of enterprises remains at about 11.9%, which indicates the need to strengthen managerial, financial and institutional mechanisms to support innovation [3].

Digital transformation opens up new opportunities for SMEs, but at the same time increases competition. Companies that use digital technologies only as an auxiliary tool run the risk of harming enterprises that are able to build full-fledged digital business models. Therefore, innovation activity management should be focused not only on the implementation of individual software solutions, but also on changing the logic of doing business.

The development of e-commerce is of particular importance. The growth in the volume of retail electronic commerce from 482.0 billion tenge in 2021 to 3,768.8 billion tenge in 2025 shows that digital sales channels are becoming the most important factor of competitiveness [2]. However, for the sustainable development of SMEs, it is necessary to ensure a balance between the use of marketplaces and the development of enterprises' own digital assets.

Conclusion. Managing the innovation activity of small and medium-sized businesses in the context of the digital transformation of the economy is the most important direction for increasing the competitiveness of Kazakhstan. The analysis showed that the SME sector plays a significant role in the national economy: as of January 1, 2025, 2,071.7 thousand SMEs operated in Kazakhstan, 4,422.1 thousand people were employed in the sector, and the output of products in 2024 amounted to 81,920.0 billion tenge [1]. At the same time, the level of innovative activity of enterprises remains limited and requires systematic support.

Digital transformation creates conditions for the growth of innovative activity of SMEs through e-commerce, digital platforms, automation of processes, data analytics and new financial technologies. However, to

realize this potential, an integrated approach is needed, including the development of digital infrastructure, increasing the competencies of entrepreneurs, affordable financing, institutional support and the formation of regional innovation ecosystems.

The practical significance of the research lies in the fact that the proposed model for managing SME innovation activity can be used in the development of programs to support entrepreneurship, digitalize business and increase the competitiveness of the regional economy.

References

1. Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan. (2025). Monitoring of small and medium-sized businesses in the Republic of Kazakhstan as of January 1, 2025. Available at: <https://stat.gov.kz/en/industries/business-statistics/stat-org/publications/350850/>
2. Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan. (2025). E-commerce in the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2025. Available at: <https://stat.gov.kz/en/industries/economy/local-market/publications/488906/>
3. Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan. (2025). On the innovative activity of enterprises in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Available at:

<https://stat.gov.kz/en/industries/social-statistics/stat-edu-science-inno/spreadsheets/>

4. World Bank. (2024). World Bank to help expand digital infrastructure for underserved areas in Kazakhstan. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2024/02/22/world-bank-to-help-expand-digital-infrastructure-for-underserved-areas-in-kazakhstan>
5. United Nations. (2024). E-Government Survey 2024: Kazakhstan country data. Available at: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Data/Country-Information/id/87-Kazakhstan>
6. World Intellectual Property Organization. (2025). Global Innovation Index 2025. Available at: https://www.wipo.int/global_innovation_index/
7. Portulans Institute. (2025). Network Readiness Index 2025: Kazakhstan country profile. Available at: <https://download.networkreadinessindex.org/reports/countries/2025/kazakhstan.pdf>
8. Schumpeter, J.A. (1934). *The Theory of Economic Development*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
9. Gonzalez-Varona, J.M., Lopez-Paredes, A., Poza, D. and Acebes, F. (2024). Building and development of an organizational competence for digital transformation in SMEs. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.01615>
10. World Bank. (2024). Kazakhstan Enterprise Survey 2024. Available at: <https://microdata.worldbank.org/index.php/catalog/6688>